

**ANXIETY AS AN EFFECTIVE FACTOR IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE
LEARNING**

Isroilova Jasmina Yusub kizi,

University of Exact and Social Sciences, master's student

Email: sjasmine1126@gmail.com

Scientific adviser: **Abdul Khaeva Malika Maratovna**

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, PhD

Email: abdul Khaeva.malika@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article examines foreign language anxiety (FLA) as a significant affective factor influencing foreign language learning. The study aims to analyze the nature of language anxiety, its main factors, and its impact on learners' performance. The paper, based on theoretical and empirical research in applied linguistics, explores anxiety as a distinct emotional reaction that can both support and impede language acquisition. The analysis identifies three major categories of anxiety predictors: linguistic factors, learner-internal factors, and learner-external factors. The results indicate that although anxiety can sometimes serve as a source of motivation, it generally has a detrimental impact on learners' speaking performance and self-expression. The study highlights the need to create a supportive learning environment and to implement learner-centered approaches to reduce anxiety levels and improve language learning outcomes.

Key words: foreign language anxiety, specific anxiety reaction, linguistic factors, learner-internal factors, learner-external factors, perfectionism, self-evaluation

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается иностранная языковая тревожность

(FLA) как значимый аффективный фактор, влияющий на изучение иностранного языка. Целью исследования является анализ природы языковой тревожности, ее основных факторов и влияния на успеваемость учащихся. В статье, основанной на теоретических и эмпирических исследованиях в области прикладной лингвистики, тревога рассматривается как особая эмоциональная реакция, которая может как способствовать, так и препятствовать овладению языком. Анализ выделяет три основные категории предикторов тревоги: лингвистические факторы, внутренние факторы учащегося и внешние факторы учащегося. Результаты показывают, что, хотя тревога иногда может служить источником мотивации, она обычно оказывает пагубное влияние на речевую деятельность и самовыражение учащихся. В исследовании подчеркивается необходимость создания благоприятной среды обучения и внедрения подходов, ориентированных на учащихся, для снижения уровня тревожности и улучшения результатов изучения языка.

Ключевые слова: иноязычная тревожность, специфическая тревожная реакция, лингвистические факторы, внутренние факторы учащегося, внешние факторы учащегося, перфекционизм, самооценка

Introduction.

No doubt learning foreign languages has become increasingly popular across the globe. This pattern of growth is mainly attributed to globalization, migration, technological advancements, and the growing need for intercultural communication. Statistical data clearly show this trend: approximately 1.2–1.5 billion people worldwide are currently learning a foreign language, with English the most widely studied. [1] Furthermore, the global language learning market has grown rapidly, reaching over \$83 billion in 2025 and is projected to exceed \$188 billion by 2030, translating into a steady rise in demand for language education. [2] However, the methods and approaches used to learn foreign languages vary

significantly across different regions and educational contexts. As a result, learners encounter different challenges during the language acquisition process: linguistic constraints (vocabulary limitations, grammatical difficulties), cognitive demands (information processing, working memory load), and affective variables (motivation, self-confidence, anxiety). Anxiety, particularly, is one of the most common difficulties encountered by foreign language learners.

Materials and methods.

“Many people claim to have a mental block against learning a foreign language, although these same people may be good learners in other situations, strongly motivated, and have a sincere liking for speakers of the target language... In many cases, they may have an anxiety reaction which impedes their ability to perform successfully in a foreign language class,” [4] say Elaine K. Horwitz, Michael B. Horwitz, and Joann Cope in their article “Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety”. Indeed, many learners are fast learners and/or are driven by a strong motivation to learn a new language, but fail to achieve. All this is due to “foreign language anxiety” as authors mentioned. Then, what is the anxiety itself? Anxiety is a subjective feeling of tension and apprehension that may jeopardize the efficiency of one’s language performance. Just as anxiety can hinder people from succeeding in mathematics or science, many find learning foreign languages stressful, particularly in a classroom environment. Such cases are referred to as “specific anxiety reaction”. Psychologists use this term to describe people who feel anxious in specific circumstances, rather than those who are generally anxious in various situations.

Scholars have identified language anxiety as one of the major obstacles to be overcome when learning to speak foreign languages. So, what are the main causes of Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA)? “Guora argues that language learning itself is “a profoundly unsettling psychological proposition” because it directly threatens an individual’s self-concept and worldview,” say Elaine K. Horwitz, Michael B.

Horwitz, and Joann Cope. [4; 6] Every language represents a distinct worldview. Thus, one may experience a psychological paradox, as they are required to interpret and/or express meaning in a completely new linguistic system while relying on their existing cognitive and cultural frameworks.

According to Mostafa Papi and Hassan Khajavy, “A person’s perception of achievement can lead to the emotional response of enjoyment, whereas their failures can arouse the emotional response of disappointment. Similarly, a person’s perception of the existence of safety and security can lead to the emotional response of calmness, whereas the perceived existence of risk perceptions can generate fear or anxiety.” It can be learned from the statement that a possible trigger of anxiety is the risk of danger. The sense of danger is, subsequently, closely connected to emotions that reflect each individual’s anticipation of a possible future. Mostafa Papi and Hassan Khajavy believe that the emotional response of anxiety can carry both positive and negative impacts on foreign language learning (FLL). As claimed, emotional response of anxiety helps learners to be ready for the anticipated negative consequences that may or may not happen immediately or in the near or distant future. However, it can also harm the student’s language performance due to its “inhibitory effects on learners’ L2 comprehension and use.” Many learners report experiencing trembling, sweating, and tension in their foreign language classes, particularly when underperforming, overstudying, losing their words in the middle of a speech, being unable to verbalize their thoughts, feeling confused or distracted, etc. [4]

Results and discussion.

Mostafa Papi and Hassan Khajavy present three categories of FLA sources: linguistic, learner-internal, and learner-external factors.

With respect to linguistic factors in foreign language anxiety, Sparks and Ganschow believe that anxiety aroused by learning a second language is closely connected to challenges one experiences in one's native language; language

aptitude is a prime example. [5; 7] However, other researchers, particularly MacIntyre, criticized this view, claiming that there are many other factors involved in producing second language anxiety apart from the first language skills. [8] One of such triggers is the language learner's "self-perceived language proficiency." It was found that language learners with higher self-perceived proficiency in the target language are less anxious because they have the necessary skills to accomplish relevant tasks and/or activities, whereas those with fewer achievements or lower self-proficiency experience higher levels of linguistic anxiety. Another linguistic factor for foreign language anxiety is multilingualism. Multilinguals are more confident when learning and/or performing in a new language due to their prior experience with second-language learning, or it may be linked to higher metalinguistic knowledge, which could help them decrease L2 anxiety. [5] Moreover, Thompson and Lee have found that multilingualism does not guarantee low or absent linguistic anxiety unless the learner has at least intermediate proficiency in the target language. [9] Frequent use of words or phrases in the target language in one's regular speech is another important linguistic factor associated with FLA. Jiang Y. and Dewaele argue that learners who use the target language more often have higher self-perceived proficiency levels and, subsequently, experience lower anxiety levels. [5; 10]

Learner-internal factors can also influence the foreign language learners' anxiety level. M. Papi and H. Khajavy have classified these predictors into two groups: sociobiographical and psychological. [5] When learners' age and gender are considered as sociobiographical factors, their motivation to learn the target language and personality traits, such as competitiveness or low self-esteem, are psychological predictors that might translate into overall anxiety levels in a foreign language. In their research on applied linguistics, S. Mercer and S. Ryan have identified two types of mindsets: the L2 growth mindset and the L2 fixed mindset. [11] If the L2 growth mindset is the belief that language-learning ability can be

acquired through hard work, the fixed mindset holds that this ability is innate and cannot be improved. Scholars' research has shown that a fixed mindset might be a source of language anxiety, while a growth mindset prompts positive emotions like happiness or joy. Research has also proved that people with a fixed mindset worry about other people's judgment, whereas people with a growth mindset pay little attention to the judgment of people around them. Personality traits are the other distinctive contributor to language anxiety. Extraversion, for example, is a negative predictor of linguistic anxiety, primarily because extroverted people tend to take risks more frequently than introverted people. Emotional intelligence is another negative predictor of linguistic anxiety. Learners with higher emotional intelligence are more resilient to anxiety, as they can manage their own emotions and better gauge the emotional reactions of others.

The third source of language anxiety is linguistic-external factors, which arise from the learning environment rather than from an inner state of the learner. Harsh error corrections, limited use of the target language, and strictness of a teacher were identified as negative external factors, while positive teacher attitude in the classroom, encouraging teaching style were associated with lower anxiety. [5]

Kayavo V. A., on the other hand, defined two sources of language anxiety: external factors and internal(personal) factors. She claimed that the tuition system in Greek and Turkish schools puts the result and preparation for exams at the center of the overall program, which causes language anxiety. The researcher also mentions other countries like Iran and China, pointing out that a foreign language (particularly, English) is learnt as a compulsory subject in these countries; students study grammar and vocabulary, while the significance of speaking and listening skills is neglected. It eventually prompts language anxiety, primarily because learners get anxious about their marks and the load of study. The classroom environment is another important factor. A formal, teacher-centered classroom,

where there is no room for mistakes, as they are harshly corrected, results in linguistic anxiety and reduces learners' willingness to participate in classroom activities.

Regarding internal factors, Kayavo V. A. mainly discusses the role of age and personality traits (i.e., perfectionism and self-evaluation). The researcher believes the role of age cannot be fully explained, as research works conducted in this field were not tailored for all age brackets. With respect to perfectionism, she mentions H. Luo and J.-M. Dewaele's ideas. They found out that the perfectionist students have a higher level of anxiety, primarily because they find it difficult to meet the high standards they set. Likewise, anxiety also influences the level of perfectionism, prompting self-criticism; as a result, anxious students react harshly to their own mistakes and become less satisfied with their performance. [12; 13]

Conclusion.

Foreign language anxiety is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon that plays a crucial role in foreign language learning. The analysis has shown that anxiety stems from a combination of linguistic, internal, and external factors, each shaping learners' emotional and cognitive experiences in different ways. While a certain degree of anxiety may sometimes enhance learners' readiness and awareness, high levels of anxiety generally influence the language performance negatively.

The study highlights that the learners' self-perception, personality traits, and mindset have a significant impact on their anxiety levels, while the role of teachers and the overall classroom environment is equally important. Therefore, educators ought to acknowledge the impact of anxiety and implement strategies that create a low-pressure and supportive learning atmosphere. Addressing foreign language anxiety not only improves academic performance but also enhances learners' overall engagement and motivation in the language learning process. Reducing foreign language anxiety not only improves academic performance but also

enhances learner engagement and motivation throughout the language learning process.

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